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Abstract:

This document is a report accompanying the SSHOC D4.7 Code for data exchange between TMT and open-source CAT software. The team has explored possibilities for data exchange between TMT and CAT tools, specifically MateCat and MyMemory, finding three areas where such a connection would be worthwhile to develop. As a first exploration, the team has focussed on TMT and MyMemory for single segment translation suggestions, resulting in the development of a demo tool.

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Incorporate comments by SSHOC coordinators	08/03/2021	Sebastiaan Pennings

Note on Time Schedule before Delivery

In the first quarter of 2020, the Task team decided to investigate the possibility of data exchanges between the Translation Management Tool (TMT), developed by CentERdata, and various open-source CAT tools. Part of the reason for this was that similar work was also being done to connect TMT to the LINDAT translation service.

The second quarter was used to explore CAT tools, which resulted in the selection of MateCat and MyMemory, with the latter being the most suitable for a first implementation (see Paragraph 4 for the reasoning behind this). Also, in this and part of the third quarter, work was done on the implementation of a demo tool, which was finalized in late September 2020.

The remaining time of the third quarter was used to validate the resulting tool and creating a final report on the process.

Executive Summary

One of the goals of SSHOC is leveraging and interconnecting existing and new infrastructure from SSH ERICs. As part of this effort and more specifically task D4.7, the CentERdata team has explored possibilities for data exchange between TMT and CAT (Computer assisted translation) tools such as MateCat and MyMemory. For this purpose, the team has explored the general functionality of these tools and looked at possible areas where a connection between them would be feasible and worthwhile. For one of these areas a demo tool was implemented.

TMT is a web-based tool developed by CentERdata to support the translation process of large multicultural and multilingual surveys, such as SHARE, ESS, EVS and others. It has a specific focus on questionnaire translation and allows the reuse of translations in longitudinal studies.

MateCat is a freely accessible open-source CAT tool for the translation of collections of text such as documents. It offers options for machine translation, translation based on public Translation Memory and translation by translators.

MyMemory is a large, publicly available source for translation memories, initially sourced from European Union and United Nations projects and populated by any translators using MateCat. It provides a search-like lookup of translated segments for a great number of language pairs in various subject domains and is used extensively by MateCat.

The team has identified three areas where data exchange between these tools is worth exploring: 1) use of MyMemory for per-segment translation within the TMT interface; 2) use of MateCat for full questionnaire translations at the start of a project in TMT, based on an initial source version; and 3) export of TMT data for the purpose of contributing to MyMemory.

For the current exploration, the team has focussed on the first area as this was already in line with other work connecting the LINDAT translation services to TMT. The implementation consists of an independent demo tool that allows users to enter text segments, which are communicated to the MyMemory service. The suggestions returned by MyMemory are then presented to the user. Each suggestion includes source language segments and translations, as well as a “matching score” (a measure of how closely suggestions made by MyMemory match the entered text segment). Suggestions with high matching scores are generally good but will require approval by the user to ensure translation quality.

A conclusion reached is that a per-segment connection between TMT and MyMemory is feasible and adds value to the former, especially because a similar development with LINDAT translation has already been integrated into TMT. The project team has not done any implementation work for the remaining two areas, because these have far more complex translation quality and implementation considerations that are beyond the scope of this task. However, the CentERdata team is of the opinion that it is worth further exploring these possibilities in future research.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
TMT	Translation Management Tool
LINDAT	Part of LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ, Acronym of “Digital Research Infrastructure for Language Technologies, Arts and Humanities.”
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (http://www.share-project.org)
ESS	European Social Survey (https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org)
EVS	European Values Study (https://europeanvaluesstudy.eu)
CAT	Computer Aided Translation
PHP	PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor. A general purpose scripting language, mainly used in the development of web applications (https://www.php.net/).
TRAPD	Translation, Review, Adjudication, Pretest, Documentation. A method for survey translation.
XML	Extensible Markup Language. An open standard markup language defining a set of rules for documents that are both human- and machine-readable.
API	Application Programming Interface. A computing interface defining interaction between separate programs. APIs often allow client software to interact with server applications.
GET request	A GET request is an HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol) method, used to request data from a specified (internet) resource
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation, a data human-readable data exchange format.

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1. Introduction

This document describes the CentERdata team's exploration into a connection between the Translation Memory Tool (TMT) and CAT tools, specifically MateCat and MyMemory. It aims to inform those that are involved with the development of TMT and any of the explored tools on the possibilities of data exchange between the tools and serves as an explanation for the implemented demo tool (see Section 4).

Within the SSHOC project, one goal is leveraging and interconnecting existing and new infrastructure from SSH ERICs. Task D4.7 looks specifically at exploring this for TMT and open-source CAT tools. TMT, a web-based tool developed by CentERdata, provides a translation environment for large multicultural and multilingual surveys and contains translated texts for these surveys. However, it does not have an extended translation memory functionality, meaning connection with open-source CAT tools that do have such functionality may improve usability. Actual implementation within TMT is outside the scope of this task, but may be a consideration at a later point. Conversely, TMT data may be useful to other tools as such data can be used for translation memory purposes.

The three tools will be introduced in Section 2. Section 3 will discuss the data exchange. In Section 4 implementation is discussed, and in Section 5 a conclusion is presented.

2. Tools

2.1 TMT

TMT is a web-based tool developed by CentERdata to support the translation process of large multicultural and multilingual surveys, such as SHARE, ESS, EVS and others.

The tool is specifically designed to support the translation of questionnaires following the 'team' or 'committee approach' or TRAPD process, which is state-of-the-art in academic questionnaire translation (Harkness 2003). It splits a source questionnaire description up into related segments, such as question texts, interviewer instructions, response options and fill variables. For scripted questionnaires, it provides support to manage the translation of any software related texts, such as that of buttons, pop-up texts, etc. Translation process managers can add information such as translator instructions, action points and annotations and upload documents to guide translators with their work. Participants in the process can communicate within the tool.

TMT can work as an integrated part of the development process of more complex questionnaires and interviewing instruments and can import and export a number of formats, including (but not limited to) XML, Excel, Quest and Blaise definitions.

For longitudinal studies, TMT allows for the reuse of existing translations from previous waves/rounds that are stored in the system.

Finally, TMT provides access to translation suggestions from LINDAT translations.

2.2 MateCat

MateCat is an open-source CAT tool that offers a freely accessible service to translate source documents into a variety of languages.

It is accessible via the tool's website, which offers a web interface where documents can be directly uploaded for translation. Unfortunately, this web interface currently only seems to work in Google Chrome. The interface allows users to choose language pairs, a subject and a project name if so desired. By default, MateCat uses MyMemory for its translations, which includes Translation Memory and Machine Translation (Google translate, Microsoft Translator), although other sources can also be used and new translation memories can be added.

MateCat currently supports 72 file formats, including many Microsoft office, web and localization formats. As such, it is especially useful when translating such large collections of text.

2.3 MyMemory

MyMemory is a large, publicly available source for translation memories, sourced from European Union and United Nations projects. It provides a search-like lookup of translated segments for a great number of language pairs in various subject domains. It also contains translations by users of MateCat because default settings in MateCat automatically add users' translations to MyMemory.

It provides a web interface much like MateCat, where text can be entered, and a language pair can be chosen. Subsequent results include machine-translated suggestions, as well as suggestions from human contributions. It is however not entirely clear what translation engine is used in the background, meaning further investigation is needed.

3. Possible data exchange

Data exchange between TMT and other CAT software can be established in a variety of ways. The exact implementation depends largely on the task you are trying to automate. Furthermore, some implementations may benefit different user roles within the system more than others. Such roles may vary across projects, but typically include *managers* overseeing one or more specific languages within a country, *translators* translating source texts into a specific language and *verifiers* checking translation quality.

The following processes can be (semi-)automated:

- Per-segment translation suggestions
- Automatic translation of entire questionnaires
- Upload of TMT data to Translation Memory services

3.1 Per-segment translation suggestions

In this case, data exchange is in the form of individual requests by TMT to outside sources, such as a web service. Input variables for such a request would include a segment of the source text for a single item in the questionnaire and a language pair, the source language commonly being English. The response by the external service would include a set of suggestions for the given segment.

The most fitting suggestion is chosen and edited directly by a user within TMT. Possibly, quality indicators that come with the suggestions may determine the order in which suggestions are presented to the user. A functionality such as this would primarily benefit users with the role of translator.

A direct connection to a service like MyMemory is best suited for this kind of task, and it is what the team has chosen for this implementation, as it closely follows other work the team has also done in connecting to LINDAT translations (see paragraph 1). You will find the code for this implementation with this document.

3.2 Automatic translation of entire questionnaires

In this case, instead of translating on a per-segment basis, the entirety of the questionnaire is fed into an external service for a pre-translation in a single call. Parameters would include the full questionnaire in the standard TMT XML export format, together with a language pair, where again the source is commonly English. A response would be a fully translated XML document that could then be reimported into TMT to fill the target language. Because there is no guarantee for the quality of these imported translations, the development of post-editing functionality is likely required. This functionality too could benefit translators, but may also be used by managers to provide an initial translation.

A connection to MateCat would be most sensible here due to its focus on the translation of entire documents, instead of small segments. However, as each source text segment can have multiple suggestions, it may prove difficult to fully automate such a task without there being the need for a human translator to evaluate the suggestions.

Exploring this kind of data exchange may be worthwhile in the future, but because of its complexity, it is left out of the scope of this current exploration.

3.3 Upload of TMT data to Translation Memory services

Finally, as translations within TMT are done for a number of large European studies, it would most likely be worthwhile to investigate the possibility of automatic export of translation sets from TMT to external

Translation Memory services like MyMemory. This could, for instance, be done via exports from TMT in the form of TMX files. Such a functionality would likely mainly be used by managers or top-level administrators of TMT who are willing to create synergies by sharing translation output.

Looking into this kind of data exchange further may be worthwhile in the future. As the generating and exporting of TMX files will most likely prove trivial, any future exploration should focus more on the problem of determining the quality of translations provided from TMT – and also on clarifying any legal issues, e.g. with regard to the intellectual property of the individual translations.

4. Implementation and demo tool

As mentioned in the previous paragraph, the team has chosen to primarily focus on data exchange between TMT and MyMemory in the form of per-segment suggestions. For this, the team has developed a small, independent tool to demonstrate how this exchange would work. This tool and its source code are available under a GPL license. Implementation was done in PHP¹ with Bootstrap 3.3².

The tool presents a basic input form. For source text input, there is a text area titled “Original text”. In a fully integrated implementation, this would be fed with data from TMT directly. The user should select a language pair, choosing the source and target language.

FIGURE 1: INITIAL SCREEN, INCLUDING AN EXAMPLE TEXT

Upon clicking the forms’ “translate” button, the tool makes a request directly to the MyMemory API, which in turn sends back a response including a list of suggestions.

Once the button is clicked, a GET request is sent to the MyMemory API in the following form:

```
https://api.mymemory.translated.net/get?q=[query_text]&langpair=[lang_from][lang_to]
```

Where [query_text] is a URL-encoded string value containing the source text that needs to be translated, [lang_from] is the locale code for the source language and [lang_to] is the locale for the target language.

¹ PHP - <https://www.php.net> [accessed 16 Mar 2021]

² Bootstrap - <https://getbootstrap.com/docs/3.3/> [accessed 16 Mar 2021]

Please note that the query text is sent as variable *q*, whilst *lang_from* and *lang_to* are combined into a single variable, *langpair*.

The resulting dataset returned by the MyMemory API is in a JSON format that is structured as the following:

Response (JSON format)

- responseData (array)
 - translatedText (string)
 - match (float)
- quotaFinished (Boolean)
- mtLangSupported
- responseDetails (string)
- responseStatus (string) – result code for the request
- responderId (string)
- exception_code
- matches (array) – holds a list of suggestions
 - id (string) – internal id for the returned segment
 - segment (string) – source language segment found for query text (*lang_from*)
 - translation (string) – target language segment containing translation (*lang_to*)
 - source (string) – source locale (*lang_from*)
 - target (string) – target locale (*lang_to*)
 - quality (integer) – quality score for the suggestion. In many cases, this value will be 0. As such, it is not clear how useful this value is.
 - reference
 - usage-count (integer)
 - subject (string) - subject from which the suggestion was taken, f.i. "All" or "Legal and Notarial"
 - created-by (string) – the corpora from which the suggestion came, f.i. "Public corpora" or "MT!"
 - last-update-by (string)
 - create-date (string) – suggestion creation date in YYYY-mm-dd HH:ii:ss format
 - last-update-date (string) – format in YYYY-mm-dd HH:ii:ss format
 - match (float) – match score, from 0 to 1
 - model (string) – f.i. "neural", not always part of the response.

This result is parsed by the *TMemory* class' *getSuggestions* function, which iterates through the "match" array in the structure, loading the values within each element into a *TMemorySuggestion* object. This object parses the values and stores them. The "match" score is then taken and compared to the other *TMemorySuggestion* objects. The highest score is chosen as the "prime" suggestion, which appears together with its match score. The team does not use the "quality" value in the implementation, as it is often zero.

Currently, the “prime” suggestion will match the suggestion given in the responseData element. Although this option can be taken directly, the choice was to iterate the list of suggestions within *TMemory* as the team has no control over the primary suggestion that is given by the response itself. Furthermore, the suggestion in responseData only contains a translated text and accompanying match score, but does not have any of the extra information provided in the “matches” array.

If it is wished to automatically choose suggestions in a future implementation, the team should look at how the “match” and “quality” values are determined and how they can best be used to select a good prime suggestion.

Once the suggestions are parsed, the result is shown on screen, with the prime suggestion on the right side of the input form panel. Below, all suggestions are shown as a list that includes the source and target segments, as well as a match and quality score and information on the creators/updaters, date and time. Finally, the request value and raw response data are shown at the bottom of the screen.

Original text

Language pairs:

From

To

Prime suggestion (match=0.89)

Results					
Segment	Translation	Match	Quality	Created	Last updated
This is an example :	Beispiel :	0.89	0	translatathon <small>2013-10-15 14:57:03</small>	translatathon <small>2013-10-15 14:57:03</small>
This is an example:	Dies ist ein Beispiel:	0.88	0	Public_Corpora <small>2018-02-13 12:20:53</small>	Public_Corpora <small>2018-02-13 12:20:53</small>
This is an example text	Dies ist ein Beispieltext	0.85	70	MT! <small>2020-09-28 13:45:03</small>	MT! <small>2020-09-28 13:45:03</small>

Request sent: <https://api.mymemory.translated.net/get?q=This+is+an+example+text&langpair=en-GB|de-DE>

Raw data

```
array(8) {
  ["responseData"]=>
  array(2) {
    ["translatedText"]=>
```

FIGURE 2: SCREEN SHOWING THE RESULTS RETRIEVED FROM MYMEMORY

Further documentation on TMemory and TMemorySuggestion can be found in the PHP code provided along with this document.

Response data returned by MyMemory can be further explored in the “Raw data” panel displayed after each query. This shows the parsed JSON data.

4.1 Installation

If you want to run the demo code yourself, you will need the following: apache 2.4 (or higher) and php 7.3 (or higher). Copy the contents of the "sourcecode" folder into your apache htdocs directory.

Once installed, you can run the demo by calling the TMemory.php file.

4.2 Example source texts and resulting suggestions

Source text: How old is the respondent?	Language pair: en-GB de-DE	Prime suggestion: Wie alt ist der Befragte? [match=0.85] Other suggestions: Wie alt ist das Universum? [match=0.67] Wie alt ist die Erde? [match=0.66]
Source text: How many children does the respondent have?	Language pair: en-GB it-IT	Prime suggestion: Quanti figli ha l'intervistato? [match=0.85] Other suggestions: Quanti bambini hai? [match=0.63] Quanti figli/e ha? [match=0.62]
Source text: In welke maand bent u geboren?	Language pair: nl-NL fr-FR	Prime suggestion: En quel mois êtes-vous né? [match=0.85] Other suggestions: En quelle année êtes-vous né(e) ? [match=0.63] En quelle année êtes-vous né ? [match=0.62]
Source text: In welchem Jahr haben Sie geheiratet?	Language pair: de-DE en-GB	Prime suggestion: What year did you get married? [match=0.85] Other suggestions: In which year did you receive the bachelor diploma (or equivalent)? [match=0.66] When did you get married?" [match=0.63]

5. Conclusion

The aim for task D4.7 was an exploration into possible data exchange between TMT and open-source CAT tools leading to the creation of code showing such an exchange. Further exploration into data exchange between TMT and external CAT tools seems promising.

The created demo tool shows us that the MyMemory service can be used as an external source for translation suggestions based on translation memory. It is the team's opinion that integration of per-segment translation suggestions into TMT should definitely be considered, especially since this would be a logical addition to the functionality already provided within TMT with the connection to LINDAT translations.

Full questionnaire pre-translations will speed up the initial translation of new questionnaires, although it will not affect the need for or speed of translation quality assessment. Further exploration into a connection between TMT and MateCat would be good. However, for longitudinal studies with repeated questions and smaller changes, it may be more efficient to base suggestions directly on items translated in earlier waves/rounds.

Finally, exporting translations from TMT in order to contribute to other external services may also be worthwhile as it would make TMT data more easily available, but this should only be considered if the quality of exported translations can be properly evaluated, involved stakeholders agree to such an export and any legal issues have been resolved.

6. References

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